

Search for New Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part V

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Synthesis of some new 1-aryl-5-*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene- and 1-aryl-5-furfurylidene-hydantoin and -2-thiohydantoin are described.

The active use of *N*¹-alkyl-*N*²-arylsulphonylureas in oral control of diabetes is well known. The active moiety is built in hydantoins and 2-thiohydantoins and these are reported to have lowered the blood-sugar level in mammals'. Elgee *et al.*² observed that administration of 5-isopropylidene-2,4-dithiohydantoin orally or by intravenous injections inhibited insulin degradation in rats. William *et al.*³ found that hydantoin inhibited beef-liver enzyme system which degraded insulin. It is known that inhibition of degradation of insulin lowers the blood-sugar level. These observations suggest hydantoins as a protection against diabetes. Paul *et al.*⁴ and Dhar *et al.*⁵ synthesised a number of 8-substituted hydantoinic esters, 3- or 5-substituted hydantoins, and some corresponding thiohydantoins for testing their hypoglycemic activity. Roy and co-workers⁶ reported their hypoglycemic activity in albino rats. They found that 4-ethyl-8-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-hydantoinate, 3-phenylhydantoin, 3-(2',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)hydantoinate, and 3-octylhydantoin exhibited hypoglycemic activity of the same order as that obtained with BZ.55. Seymour *et al.*⁷ prepared dimethylbiguanidine derivative of hydantoin which possessed hypoglycemic activity. 1-(*p*-Toluenesulphonyl)- and 1-(*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-alkyl-substituted hydantoins were found to be hypoglycemic in rats⁸. Recently Holan *et al.*⁹ prepared many 3-alkyl-1-arylsulphonyl-hydantoins and -2-thiohydantoins, possessing marked hypoglycemic activity.

It has already been discussed that furan group in association with other grouping is responsible for the activity¹⁰ and further, Seymour *et al.*⁷ prepared a few biguanide and 2-furylbiguanide derivatives of antidiabetic property.

Several compounds related to hypoglycin A, possessing hypoglycemic activity, have been prepared by Anderson¹¹. Their studies suggest that terminal ethylenic linkage is

1. Ishiki, *Pharmacol. Japan*, 1932, 15, No. 1, Breviaria 4.
2. *Proc. Soc. Exptl. Biol. Med.*, 1954, 87, 67.
3. *Metabolism, Clin. and Exptl.* (University of Washington, Seattle), 1959, 8, pp. 99-113.
4. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18 C, 21.
5. *Ibid.*, 1961, 20 C, 145.
6. *Ibid.*, 1960, 19 C, 75.
7. U.S.P. 2961377/1960.
8. Budesinsky *et al.*, *Czechoslov. farmac.*, 1960, 9, 466.
9. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4660.
10. Tiwari and Swaroop, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 394.
11. Anderson *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 330.

responsible for the activity when it is separated from the potential grouping by two or three carbon atoms.

Holland and co-workers¹² found that most acidic compounds were more active hypoglycemic agent. Compounds containing $-C_6H_4NMe_2(p)$ grouping are exceptions as these are less acidic and still very active.

Keeping the aforesaid considerations in view, we have prepared hydantoin (I and II) which have ethylenic linkage with other active groupings combined in one molecule.

(I)

(II)

In the present investigation *para*-substituted monoaryl ureas and thioureas were prepared and these were condensed with monochloroacetic acid in pyridine to furnish 1-substituted hydantoin and thiohydantoin. These hydantoin and thiohydantoin were condensed with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and furfural separately. The melting point, yield, and analysis etc. of the compounds are recorded in Tables I—V.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-(Substituted phenyl)hydantoin.—An equimolecular (0.2*M*) mixture of monochloroacetic acid and each of phenylurea, *p*-tolylurea, *p*-anisylurea, and *p*-chlorophenylurea separately taken in anhydrous pyridine (10 ml). The suspension was warmed on a water bath. An exothermic reaction raised the temperature of suspension to 80°. The solution was then refluxed for 15 minutes. After cooling, a syrupy mass was obtained. Absolute ethanol was added to it. The corresponding hydantoin separating were recrystallised from methanol.

1-(Substituted phenyl)-2-thiohydantoin.—Substituted phenylthiourea (0.2*M*) and monochloroacetic acid (0.2*M*) were taken in anhydrous pyridine (15 ml). The suspension was warmed. An exothermic reaction raised the temperature of suspension to 80°. After cooling, absolute ethanol was added to the syrupy mass which was refluxed for 10 minutes and cooled. The 2-thiohydantoin separating were recrystallised from methanol.

1-Aryl-5-*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidenehydantoin.—A mixture of 0.01*M* each of 1-phenyl-, 1-*p*-toluyl-, 1-*p*-anisyl, and 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-hydantoin and 0.01*M* of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, fused sodium acetate (1g.), and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) with a few drops of acetic anhydride was gently refluxed in an oil bath for 4 hours. Coloured crystalline product separated from the liquid. The refluxing was continued for

another hour. On cooling, crystals separating were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and recrystallised from ethyl acetate. These are very hygroscopic.

1-Aryl-5-dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-thiohydantoin.—A mixture of 1-(substituted phenyl)-2-thiohydantoin (0.01*M*), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.01*M*), and fused sodium acetate (1 g.) was taken in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and acetic anhydride (0.2ml) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours in an oil bath. On cooling, the crystals separating were collected and recrystallised from ethyl acetate. These are also hygroscopic.

1-Aryl-5-furfurylidenehydantoin.—An equimolecular mixture (0.01*M*) of 1-aryl-hydantoin and freshly distilled furfural with fused sodium acetate (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) containing few drops of acetic anhydride. The solution was refluxed for 8 hours in an oil bath. The mixture was cooled and left over calcium chloride. The shining needles separated after a week and these were recrystallised from ethyl acetate.

1-Aryl-5-furfurylidene-2-thiohydantoin.—A mixture of 1-aryl-2-thiohydantoin (0.01*M*), freshly distilled furfural (0.01*M*), fused sodium acetate (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and acetic anhydride (0.3 ml) was gently refluxed in an oil bath for 8 hours. The mixture was kept for 3 days in a calcium chloride desiccator. Silky needles separated which were recrystallised from ethyl acetate.

TABLE I
(Vide structure I)

No.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	H	205°	48%	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₂	11.46	10.94
2	Me	> 250°	52	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂	10.00	10.40
3	OMe	94°	49	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	10.25	9.79
4	Cl	98°	51	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	9.28	9.65

TABLE II
(Vide structure I; CS in place of CO)

No.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	H	154°	62%	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.90	10.30
2	Me	> 300°	61	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.32	9.79
3	OMe	102°	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ S	9.63	9.27
4	Cl	> 300°	63	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.68	9.21

TABLE III
(Vide structure II)

No.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	H	> 300°	51%	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	13.75	13.26
2	Me	178°	51	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	13.15	12.61
3	OMe	> 300°	53	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	12.60	12.10
4	Cl	89°	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.42	11.92

TABLE IV

(Vide structure II; CS in place CO)

No.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	H	178°	47%	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S	12.8	13.00
2	Me	> 250°	48	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S	12.95	12.44
3	OMe	300°	53	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	12.36	11.92
4	Cl	> 300°	40	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ON ₃ ClS	11.15	11.78

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